

EOSC WITHIN NATIONAL STRATEGIES FOR DIGITAL SKILLS

Consultation & Focus Group Report

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Executive Summary

Following the implementation of the landscape and gap analysis, and based on the results of these previous tasks as well as the emerging EOSC SRIA and Partnership documents, a structured consultation took place in November 2020 to provide insights on how to best position EOSC Skills and Training in Digital Skills in national strategies and agendas and to form the basis for developing a list of relevant recommendations for various types of policy makers. The consultation was based on two sections whereas the 1st one corresponded to identified gaps related to four "building blocks (BB)" of the Digital Skills (DS) & Open Science (OS) ecosystem (namely **People & Actors of EOSC, Processes & Governance, Policies and Technologies & infrastructure**) and the 2nd one explored the key action areas related to integrating EOSC objectives to national policies.

65 participants from 22 countries participated in the consultation, the majority of which come from the higher education and research community that are more involved and concerned with integrating EOSC skills and principles into national strategies and policies for digital upskilling.

Participants were asked to rank in terms of perceived relevance to the EOSC objectives all the gaps identified during the gap analysis phase and to nominate according to their opinion on the most pressing one for each of the above Building Blocks. They also proposed gaps that were not originally present in the consultation as relevant to the EOSC digital skills initiatives.

Furthermore, participants were asked to rank for relevance a list of provided answers for the following topics/ questions that address key aspects regarding EOSC objectives and are considered important towards elaboration of recommendations to establish EOSC positioning: 1. Digital skills required for researchers and the role of university curricula in building profiles & capacities, 2. Embed EOSC principles into the career development of researchers, Collaboration of Research, Public Sector, and Industry on Open Data, 4. Utilisation of existing human & technical infrastructures for developing learning environments and 5. The role of EOSC related skills in institutional, national, thematic, industry Digital Competence Centres in the wider national scheme.

Studying and analysis of the results (presented in this report in an easily readable graphic format) lead to the identification of 11 key areas as the basis for subsequent recommendations on EOSC positioning in national strategies. To this end, a focus group was organised in December 2020 with 17 experts from 12 countries to discuss and comment on the afore mentioned topics. They experts covered and provided expertise on policies, FAIR & Openness, EOSC leadership, researchers upskilling, researchers' career development, digital skills qualification, research ethical practice, learning environments/technologies and infrastructure, citizen's science, research upskilling governance, cross-disciplinary cooperation (research/public/industry).

The findings, presented in this report in the form of comments to proposed answers on the 11 key topics, were further analysed and lead to the final set of recommendations to be elaborated by our team to form the final deliverable of the study.

